

The impact of globalization on the Polish judiciary: the practice of Polish lawyers

At the beginning of the third decade of the 21st century, globalization is taking root in Poland, and globalization processes are also strongly affecting the Polish judiciary. This phenomenon results from the progressive integration of Poland with other European Union countries and non-EU countries, as well as with EU institutions. Particular globalization-related changes in the Polish judiciary are taking place under the influence of migration, as migrants are bringing new ideas, cultural differences, and new economic or social issues to Polish courts¹.

As a result of the progressive globalization and Europeanization of the Polish judiciary, acts of international law, mainly European Union law, are being incorporated into the domestic legal order, or directly applied. The jurisprudence of international courts also plays an increasingly important role in Poland. The Polish judiciary must adapt to these globalization phenomena, through the creation of national law and the application of international law and its interpretation, as well as through the technical, organizational, cultural and mental assimilation of international principles².

The Polish judiciary should be understood as comprising common courts and the Supreme Court, as well as administrative and provost courts, which are responsible for the application and interpretation of the law. Hence, they are subject to the globalization processes of law only in the practical and executive aspects. Therefore, we will focus more on the globalization of the processes of applying the law, rather than those of the law itself.

The common court in Poland is a multi-functional group whose purpose is to apply the law, and its primary function is distribution of justice³. As part of this, courts perform the function of judging, but also that of supporting this process. They are also administrative organizations, dealing with other organizational and technical activities for indirectly supporting basic tasks. The most important globalization changes take place within the basic function of judging, which is mainly performed by judges, but also to a limited extent by court

¹ W. Heydebrand, *From globalisation of law to law under globalisation* [w:] *Adapting Legal Cultures*, D. Nelken, J. Feest (red.), Oxford, New York 2001, s. 117–141; P. Kathrani, *Globalisation and law: the effect of globalisation on the domestic interpretation of law.*, „Jurisprudencija” 2009, nr 2 (116), s. 115–127; M.B. Steger, *Globalization: A Very Short Introduction*, Oxford 2017, s. 109–139.

² *Stosowanie prawa Unii Europejskiej przez sądy*, A. Wróbel (red.), Warszawa 2010, t.1.

³ B. Stępień-Załucka, *Sprawowanie wymiaru sprawiedliwości przez Sąd Najwyższy w Polsce*, Warszawa 2016, s. 3–67.

referendaries and associate judges (*asesor sądu*)⁴. Globalization changes are also evident in the performance of auxiliary functions in relation to judgement, which are performed by most court employees (e.g., preparation of materials, contacts with institutions, implementation of orders, delivery of correspondence, court enforcement). The broadly understood administrative activity of courts (e.g., marketing, information, management, IT services, office space) is also subject to the broad impact of globalization. The globalization phenomena that affect the judiciary are particularly visible in practical aspects of courts' functioning, including:

- application of the provisions of international law, including that of the European Union, during judgements;
- cooperation with the Luxembourg and Strasbourg tribunals (legal questions);
- execution of court judgements abroad, or foreign judgements in Poland;
- performing international technical activities, such as taking evidence abroad, delivering correspondence, translations;
- representation of the parties by foreign lawyers⁵;
- proceedings of cases on the basis of foreign law⁶;
- participation in court cases of foreign parties;
- cooperation with the European Judicial Network (EJN) and professional development in the field of cross-border cases⁷;
- the work of coordinators for international cooperation⁸.

Many globalization phenomena can be found in Polish courts; although most of them are imposed by national and international law, some result from the practice and optional activity of employees. However, despite objective factors, Polish courts do not seem to notice the broad phenomena of globalization taking place within their walls. Therefore, it is best to consider them from an external perspective. Such practices are adopted by the public administration, as well as lawyers and legal advisers. Both types of entities are not directly

⁴ J. Bodio, *Instytucja asesora sądownego*, „Studia Iuridica Lublinensia” 2010, nr 13, s. 73–89; J. Maziarz, *O niektórych praktycznych problemach związanych z przywróceniem instytucji asesora sądownego*, „Kwartalnik Krajowej Szkoły Sądownictwa i Prokuratury” 2018, nr 1 (29), s. 137–152; S. Tkacz, *Sędzia jako osoba sprawująca „wymiar sprawiedliwości”*, „Przegląd Prawa i Administracji” 2017, t. 110, nr , s. 178–203.

⁵ A. Wróbel (red.), *Stosowanie prawa Unii Europejskiej przez sądy*, *op. cit.*, t.1, s. passim.

⁶ T. Ereciński, *Ogólne zagadnienia stosowania prawa obcego przez sądy*, „Problemy Prawne Handlu Zagranicznego / Uniwersytet Śląski” 1995, nr 18, s. 75–87.

⁷ *European Judicial Network (EJN)*, https://www.ejn-crimjust.europa.eu/ejn/EJN_Home.aspx [1 listopad 2020 r.]; A. Weyembergh, I. Armada, C. Brière, *Competition or Cooperation?: State of Play and Future Perspectives on the Relations between Europol, Eurojust and the European Judicial Network*, „New Journal of European Criminal Law” 2015, t. 6, nr 2, s. 258–287.

⁸ art. 16b, 16d Ustawa z dnia 27 lipca 2001 r. Prawo o ustroju sądów powszechnych (Dz. U. z 2020 r. poz. 2072).

involved in the work of the courts, but cooperate on a regular basis. Due to their professional preparation and permanent place in the structure of the judiciary, lawyers and public institutions can provide the most detailed information on the globalization of Polish courts.

The main goal of this study is to determine and explain the scope, type and size of the impact of globalization phenomena on the Polish justice system. Particularly important are specific institutions of international law, mainly the European Union, as reflected in the process of issuing judgements (which is empirically identifiable). It is also important to determine the impact of globalization phenomena on courts' activities that are auxiliary to the function of judgement. This applies to all global phenomena that can be collectively referred to as the international activity or international turnover of Polish courts.

A pilot study was conducted with the use of a structured interview method among Polish legal advisers (*radca prawny*) and advocates (*adwokat*), and a preliminary analysis of the statistical data of the Polish judiciary, which led to the following hypotheses: (1) Polish courts are subject to very insignificant changes caused by globalization phenomena; (2) The awareness of courts (judges and other court employees) regarding the impact of globalization changes on their functioning is low and has not increased. However, there are phenomena resulting from the globalization of law (especially its enforcement) that are more often revealed in the daily work of Polish common courts.

Research methods

The results of this study are a component of a larger study on the internationalization of the Polish judiciary and legal services. The research was carried out from 7 August 2017 to 22 January 2019, and supplemented in the period from November 2020 to March 2021. The study was performed using several research methods. Triangulation allowed the results to be mutually checked, supplemented and expanded. As part of the presented research component, the research was carried out using such methods as:

1. Semi-structured in-depth interviews (SSI) with a group of 43 representatives of district councils of bar associations (*Okręgowa Rada Adwokacka, ORA*) and councils of district chambers of legal advisers (*Okręgowa Izba Radców Prawnych, OIRP*). Results were meaning-oriented. Each bar association was represented by one representative. The interviews were conducted in person and the interviews were recorded, transcribed,

coded, categorized and translated into English. The Skrybot and Atlas.ti software were used. The study is strictly qualitative in nature⁹.

2. Examination of non-reactive materials as follows: analysis of statistical data of the Polish judiciary concerning international affairs (“Oz” or “Kop”), i.e., data from the Ministry of Justice, the Central Statistical Office, the Council of Europe and the European Union (Eurostat)¹⁰; an auxiliary analysis of legal acts of the European Union and legal acts implementing this law, carried out by the legal functional method; and analysis of the content of the literature on the subject¹¹.

Detailed methodological considerations are available in the report prepared for the entire study. Source data have been stored for further use¹².

The study does not analyse all globalization phenomena affecting the Polish justice system, but only those that are empirically identified. As the research was based on the experience of lawyers and of people who prepare statistics, it is not possible to consider theoretical phenomena of globalization. Only those phenomena that are felt in reality are analysed.

The following terms often appear in the research report: “international turnover”, “legal transactions with foreign countries”, “international elements”, “foreign affairs”, “international affairs”, “international cooperation”, or the abbreviations “Oz” and “Kop”. Both abbreviations are equated with the designation of lists of international cases conducted in courts

⁹ J. Horton, R. Macve, G. Struyven, *Qualitative Research: Experiences in Using Semi-Structured Interviews* [w:] *The Real Life Guide to Accounting Research*, C. Humphrey, B. Lee (red.), Oxford 2004; S. Kvale, *Prowadzenie wywiadów*, Warszawa 2012, s. 170–178; M.J. McIntosh, J.M. Morse, *Situating and Constructing Diversity in Semi-Structured Interviews*, „Global Qualitative Nursing Research” 2015, nr 2; M. Nicpoń, R. Marzęcki, *Pogłębiony wywiad indywidualny w badaniach politologicznych* [w:] *Przeszłość, teraźniejszość, przyszłość: problemy badawcze młodych politologów*, Kraków 2010, s. 246–251; I. Przybyłowska, *Wywiad swobodny ze standaryzowaną listą poszukiwanych informacji i możliwości jego zastosowania w badaniach socjologicznych*, „Przegląd Socjologiczny” 1978, nr 30, s. 62–64; S.Q. Qu, J. Dumay, *The qualitative research interview*, „Qualitative Research in Accounting & Management” 2011, t. 8, nr 3, s. 238–261.

¹⁰ *Dynamic database of European judicial systems*, <https://www.coe.int/en/web/cepej/dynamic-database-of-european-judicial-systems> [18 kwiecień 2021 r.]; *Eurostat - database*, <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/data/database> [18 kwiecień 2021 r.]; *Główny Urząd Statystyczny*, <https://stat.gov.pl> [18 kwiecień 2021 r.]; *Informator Statystyczny Wymiaru Sprawiedliwości*, <https://isws.ms.gov.pl/pl/baza-statystyczna/> [18 kwiecień 2021 r.].

¹¹ E.R. Babbie, *Podstawy badań społecznych*, Warszawa 2008, s. 342–360; C. Frankfort-Nachmias, D. Nachmias, *Metody badawcze w naukach społecznych*, Poznań 2001; D. Kędzierski, *Metodologia i paradygmat polskich szczegółowych nauk prawnych*, „Transformacje Prawa Prywatnego” 2018, nr 3, s. 34–46.

¹² S. Lipiec, *Świadczenie międzynarodowych usług prawnych. Studium socjologiczno-prawne polskich prawników, rozprawa doktorska*.

(“Oz” is civil cases, and “Kop” is criminal)¹³. Theoretically, the scope of these two terms varies, but in practice their meanings overlap, which means that they should be treated as synonyms.

This research has a sociological dimension and is part of the broad paradigm of the sociology of law and legal anthropology. The research works of Richard Abel and Adam Podgórecki have had a great influence on its design and execution¹⁴. The general theoretical assumptions were based on the principles of grounded theory, as interpreted by Kathy Charmaz¹⁵. The guide for the interviews was Steiner Kvale¹⁶. In the case of non-reactive research (content analysis), the research was influenced by the scientific activity of Bernard Barelson, also as interpreted by Walery Pisarek¹⁷.

A similar number of legal advisers (*radcowie prawni*) and advocates (22 and 21 people, respectively), who were evenly distributed throughout the country and represented all professional associations of lawyers in Poland and supreme bodies (*Naczelna Rada Adwokacka, NRA* and *Krajowa Izba Radców Prawnych, KIRP*), participated in the empirical research, which was conducted using the interview method. The population is dominated by men (59%), as reflected in the research sample. The most professionally active group of lawyers in Poland are people aged 30 to 50, which is also seen in the research sample. It was noted that all lawyers speak at least one foreign language: English is the dominant language (62%), followed by Russian (29% of responses)¹⁸.

International cases in practice

A common measure of the internationalization of the Polish judiciary is “cases with international elements” (“Oz” cases, “Kop” cases). When advocates and legal advisers

¹³ §385, §456 Zarządzenie Ministra Sprawiedliwości z dnia 19 czerwca 2019 r. w sprawie organizacji i zakresu działania sekretariatów sądowych oraz innych działów administracji sądowej (Dz. Urz. MS.2019.138 z dnia 2019.06.21).

¹⁴ R.L. Abel, *Lawyers and the power to change*, Oxford 1985; A. Podgórecki, J. Kurczewski, *Zarys socjologii prawa*, Warszawa 1971.

¹⁵ K. Charmaz, *Teoria ugruntowana: praktyczny przewodnik po analizie jakościowej*, Warszawa 2013.

¹⁶ S. Kvale, *Prowadzenie wywiadów, op. cit.*

¹⁷ B. Berelson, *Content analysis in communication research*, New York 1971; W. Pisarek, *Analiza zawartości prasy*, Kraków 1983.

¹⁸ J. Cholewa, *Jak język polski i francuski odzwierciedla wzajemne postrzeganie Polaków i Francuzów? [w:] Anglosasi, Francuzi i Polacy: wzajemny wizerunek dawniej i dziś*, P. Guzowski, M. Kamecka (red.), Białystok 2005; K. Kloc, *Język obcy a praca w zawodzie prawnika*, https://www.goldenline.pl/grupy/Przedsiębiorcy_biznesmeni/prawo/jezyk-obcy-a-praca-w-zawodzie-prawnika,1770622/ [16 kwiecień 2020 r.]; I. Wymułek, O. Oleksiyenko, *Strukturalne zróżnicowanie znajomości języków obcych: wybrane wyniki Polskiego Badania Panelowego POLPAN 1988-2013*, Warszawa 2015.

(*radcowie prawni*), as well as court employees, hear this term, they usually answer immediately, mentioning the European Arrest Warrant (EAW) and service of correspondence abroad. The answers arise from the particular popularity of these two types of international cases among lawyers. We can see that Polish lawyers recognize as foreign affairs the implementation of specific procedures of international and EU law (EAW), and the implementation of auxiliary judicial acts originating from international or domestic law (delivery of correspondence). Judges, representatives of the administration and bar associations also add to the pool of “Oz” cases the issues of management, professional development, institutional cooperation, the activity of international coordinators, etc. It seems that “cases” are not only popular instruments of international law used in the Polish judiciary, but also concern the technical implementation of domestic, international and foreign (other countries) procedures directed abroad or coming from abroad, and other matters.

Figure 1 The popularity of international law institutions used in Polish courts according to Polish lawyers

Instruments of international law are usually introduced into the Polish legal order by transposing European Union law, or they are applied directly. The most important instruments of international criminal law are considered to be the European Arrest Warrant (EAW) and the European Investigation Warrant (EIW), as well as extradition and international arrest warrants (from outside the EU)¹⁹. In addition to international criminal procedures, civil procedures such as “small claims” are becoming increasingly important²⁰; i.e. the European Payment Order

¹⁹ *Europejskie prawo karne*, A. Grzelak (red.), Warszawa 2012, s. 404–672; M. Kusak, *Postępowanie karne w sprawach międzynarodowych: podręcznik praktyczny*, Warszawa 2017, s. 78–238.

²⁰ R. Frey, *Europejskie postępowanie w sprawie drobnych roszczeń*, „Prawo i Podatki Unii Europejskiej w Praktyce” 2008, nr 4, s. 10–13.

(EPO) and European Enforcement Order (EEO)²¹. National law or international procedures can also be implemented abroad or in an international context (in both directions). Therefore, the group of international judicial auxiliary activities includes: delivery of correspondence abroad or from abroad²², execution abroad, taking evidence abroad, and inheritance or the implementation of family law procedures abroad²³.

Such a wide range of Oz affairs causes the confluence of individual categories of cases in everyday practice. Hence, it is difficult to analyse separately the application of international law in the judiciary, the implementation of judicial support activities in international relations, and other matters. Judicial and legal practice treat all these categories together.

Advocates and legal advisers emphasize that foreign affairs are very rare in the Polish judiciary. If they do occur, most lawyers try to limit their reach and impact. This results from the belief that Polish judges and court officials are not very competent in the use of specific instruments of international law, or in the auxiliary implementation of foreign judicial elements. In the opinion of many jurists, the quality of such activities' performance by employees of Polish courts is not improving, despite the increasing number of trainings, cooperation within the European Judicial Network (EJN), appointment of international cooperation coordinators, and the specialization of individual judges and employees in the implementation of judicial foreign affairs. In the opinion of the bar representatives, if there is a foreign element in the case (usually the delivery of correspondence or evidence abroad), the case length is extended by up to four times. Moreover, the presence of foreign elements when the place of implementation is outside the European Union means that the matter may never be properly completed. In such a case, lawyers notice the abuse of suspending the proceedings, sometimes indefinitely, or even discontinuing court proceedings.

From the point of view of the parties' attorneys, cases with foreign elements appear in courts extremely rarely. They are generally not noticeable in regional courts (*sądy rejonowe*). The situation changes slightly only in district courts (*sądy okręgowe*) and courts of appeal (*sądy apelacyjne*), as courts of second instance. This trend is strongly correlated with the fact that district courts are competent to execute most instruments of international law (including EAW)

²¹ J. Pisuliński, *Europejskie prawo cywilne*, Warszawa 2009.

²² P. Domagała, A. Semeniuk, *Prawo międzynarodowe w przepisach wykonawczych do prawa o ustroju sądów powszechnych*, „Kwartalnik Krajowej Szkoły Sądownictwa i Prokuratury” 2020, nr 3 (39), s. 56–63.

²³ A. Wróbel (red.), *Stosowanie prawa Unii Europejskiej przez sądy*, *op. cit.*, t.1, s. 372–535.

and to perform judicial auxiliary activities (e.g., cross-border enforcement of maintenance)²⁴. Also in the district courts, the legislator and the executive authority have established a centre for coordination foreign affairs in the regions²⁵.

Furthermore, lawyers emphasize that in the case of regional courts, international elements are ignored, unnoticed, or “polonized”. As a consequence, they are not noticed by attorneys and the court administration. Also, judges and court employees try to treat foreign cases “in Polish” by, for example, not classifying them as Oz or Kop, insistently delivering correspondence within the country instead of abroad, or recognizing domestic jurisdiction instead of obligatory foreign jurisdiction. Lawyers also doubt the profitability of bringing small claims of a civil nature to regional courts, such as “small claims” cases, the European Payment Order (EPO) or the European Enforcement Order (EEO). The high costs of conducting such proceedings, and even greater problems with foreign enforcement, effectively prevent regional courts from conducting routine foreign activities.

Representatives of Polish advocates and legal advisers agree that the vast majority of cases with foreign elements take place in Warsaw and in several of the largest cities. The immediate cause is the lower number and importance of economic affairs taking place in the regions of the country. International companies have their headquarters in the capital, and international economic interests are conducted through Warsaw (offices, corporate headquarters, large law firms, etc.). Hence, most cases in the field of international court transactions take place in district courts in Warsaw. Additionally, Warsaw courts (*Sąd Rejonowy dla miasta stołecznego Warszawy* and *Sąd Okręgowy w Warszawie*) have default jurisdiction in certain cases of an international nature. Litigation in the field of competition and consumer protection, industrial property and patent matters, as well as the most important international arbitrations, are also conducted in the capital²⁶. The population of Warsaw, its nature as a capital, the greater number of foreign lawyers, and the functioning of the Supreme Court (*Sąd Najwyższy*) are significant. Consequently, it is the District Court in Warsaw (*Sąd Okręgowy w Warszawie*) that Polish lawyers regard as the most professional in conducting Oz cases, and which is the most burdened with such cases.

²⁴ *Alimenty: komentarz*, W. Maciejko, M. Romańska, M. Karcz, Warszawa 2016, s. 507–587.

²⁵ Rozporządzenie Ministra Sprawiedliwości z dnia 28 stycznia 2002 r. w sprawie szczegółowych czynności sądów w sprawach z zakresu międzynarodowego postępowania cywilnego oraz karnego w stosunkach międzynarodowych (Dz. U. z 2014 r. poz. 1657 z późn. zm.).

²⁶ M. Błachucki, *Sądownictwo antymonopolowe w Polsce - historia i ustrój*, Warszawa 2011, s. 11–17; K. Chłabicz, *Postępowanie sporne przed Urzędem Patentowym w przedmiocie unieważnienia praw własności przemysłowej*, „Zeszyty Prawnicze” 2017, t. 17, nr 3, s. 205–208; P. Nowaczyk, *Perspektywy rozwoju sądownictwa polubownego w Polsce*, „Kwartalnik ADR” 2009, nr 1 (5), s. 145–149.

Cases recognized as international appear in district courts also in other voivodship cities. Polish lawyers notice them, although they emphasize that their number and significance are lower than in the case of Warsaw. Essentially, in the districts, similar cases to those in Warsaw are conducted, with the exception of matters typically related to the capital. For

Figure 2 Number of cases with international elements in Polish courts according to lawyers

instance, in Wrocław and Poznań districts, a slightly larger number of foreign affairs is observed than in other voivodship cities; this is correlated with the amount of foreign investment and migration to these cities, and more foreign lawyers²⁷. Despite the noticeable number of foreign cases in these district courts, it is found that in most courts in Poland, Oz cases do not exist or are not noticed by Polish jurists. This applies to smaller provinces, and district courts established in non-provincial cities. In most regions, international matters are so rare that Polish jurists do not notice them at all.

²⁷ *Krajowy Rejestr Adwokatów i Aplikantów Adwokackich*, <https://rejestradwokatow.pl/adwokat/ewidencja> [10 marzec 2019 r.]; K. Puchalska, *Zróżnicowane polskich regionów w aspekcie bezpośrednich inwestycji zagranicznych*, „Zeszyty Naukowe Wyższej Szkoły Ekonomiczno-Społecznej w Ostrołęce” 2016, nr 21; *Rejestr radców prawnych*, <https://rejestradcow.pl> [10 marzec 2019 r.].

The geographical distribution of foreign affairs in the Polish judiciary is closely related to the types of cases. Generally, Polish lawyers do not consider court support activities and other international activities of courts, such as training, or the activities of judicial networks or of international coordinators, to be a “case type”. For Polish jurists, “case type” is a specific use of a specific legal instrument introduced by international law, or used by national law in response to it.

Lawyers emphasize that the most visible and significant issue of Oz is the use of the European Arrest Warrant: more precisely, issuing an EAW to absent clients. However, lawyers no longer notice the execution of the order abroad. Lawyers specializing in criminal matters have particular knowledge of the application of this institution; it is so well known and widespread that every lawyer point to it as a model for international affairs. Importantly, the majority emphasize that Polish courts carry out this procedure efficiently, quickly and correctly. It is disturbing that lawyers are losing sight of the execution of EAWs abroad, including bringing the wanted person to Poland. The partial participation of Polish criminalists in this procedure may lead to limiting the human rights of detainees, and lowering the quality of the execution of the order by courts and law enforcement agencies at its final stage. The issue of the EAW procedure is very widespread and thoroughly researched²⁸. Polish lawyers and legal advisers emphasize that in practice, cooperation with courts in the case of an EAW usually takes the following form, as indicated by the lawyer from Gdansk:

I have had an EAW case more than once. It is done quickly and efficiently. People are brought in by aeroplanes. For this, transport planes of the Polish army are used. Once a week, it flies all over Europe and this flight takes 14–15 hours, because it travels to all capitals and collects those arrested and detained. Then, after the arrest, it is time to appear again in court for the purpose of pre-trial detention, then it is time to possibly cooperate with the court, possibly 3.3.5. [art. 335 of the Polish Code of Criminal Procedure – St. L²⁹], so as to remove the premises which formed the basis of this arrest, although it is a very limited possibility. But then we are sure that there is a high probability that he will be in hiding. So, rather, these are very rare situations when there is an EAW and the court would refrain from applying further pre-trial detention, but theoretically it is possible. I have had matters where they bring people into Poland. And there is a kind of struggle, whether I have to be only responsible for what happened, extradition, or give up the specialty rule and abandon the case. There have been a few such cases where there have been such doubts. We usually have extraditions from public defenders, and I don't really deal with that.

²⁸ T. Gardocka, *Europejski Nakaz Aresztowania. Praktyka stosowania europejskiego nakazu aresztowania w Polsce jako państwie wydającym*, Warszawa 2011; P. Hofmański, *Europejski nakaz aresztowania w teorii i praktyce państw członkowskich Unii Europejskiej*, Warszawa 2008; L. Klimek, *European Arrest Warrant*, Cham 2014; *Praktyka stosowania europejskiego nakazu aresztowania w Polsce jako państwie wydającym*, Warszawa 2018.

²⁹ Ustawa z dnia 6 czerwca 1997 r. Kodeks postępowania karnego (Dz. U. z 2020 r. poz. 30).

The group of foreign affairs of family law is widespread among all legal specialists; however, there is no single legal institution similar to the EAW in this regard. Therefore, family matters in the international context should be examined descriptively. Lawyers note that the most important international elements in family matters are the enforcement of child support payments abroad, and parental abduction cases. The auxiliary judicial implementation of family issues is also significant; these include background surveys abroad, foreign judicial acts during proceedings regarding parental authority and childcare, cooperation with foreign family-support institutions, or foreign delivery of correspondence. The matters of divorce, the existence and division of the joint property of spouses, and the enforcement of domestic judgements abroad in family matters, are not prioritized. Legal representatives emphasize that the most important role rests with court employees, excluding judges. However, the number and complexity of cases is so large that, according to legal specialists, their execution by the bureaucracy is becoming less efficient³⁰. We can cite the following example from Katowice:

There is a mother with a child, she stays in Poland, and the father, by whom maintenance is to be paid, is abroad. And then it happens that an authority is needed to carry out the enforcement somewhere abroad, because it has to be there, the authority has to find someone there, to get the debtor and check what he has.

From the perspective of Polish legal representatives and defence lawyers, other instruments of international criminal and civil law are very rare. Also, knowledge of their existence is very limited among them, and among judges and other court employees. Usually, courts and external lawyers avoid using other international institutions and try to replace them with institutions of national law. Also encountered in judicial practice are the European Investigation Order (EIO)³¹, issues of “small claims”, the European Enforcement Order (EEO) and the European Payment Order (EPO), as well as the issue of recognizing the enforceability of judgements in Poland and abroad³². In the case of instruments of international civil procedure, lawyers agree that it is not profitable to use them for small claims. If the client requires debt enforcement from a foreign debtor, Polish jurists prefer the method of obtaining a Polish court judgement, which they then give the client, with the advice to obtain an appropriate enforcement order in another country. Lawyers generally do not represent clients in situations where it is

³⁰ *Kolizyjne i procesowe aspekty prawa rodzinnego*, J. Gołaczyński, W. Popiołek (red.), Warszawa 2019; W. Maciejko, M. Romańska, M. Karcz, *Alimenty*, *op. cit.*, s. 493–587.

³¹ A. Król, *Europejski nakaz dochodzeniowy jako kompleksowy instrument współpracy w sprawach karnych w Unii Europejskiej*, „Rocznik Administracji Publicznej” 2019, nr 5, s. 125–146.

³² K. Piasecki, *Zarys sądowego prawa procesowego Unii Europejskiej*, Warszawa 2009, s. 247–269.

necessary to resort to other options for debt collection abroad. This is how lawyers from Szczecin and Kraków describe the practice of enforcing international civil law procedures:

I have not encountered anything like this. If someone has a small cross-border claim and has to go to court with this claim, he has to find a lawyer who will do it, he has to translate the documents with a sworn translator; he usually gives up on it, because the costs of initiating this procedure are greater than the amount due. And you cannot be sure that you will get these funds back.

The only thing that actually happens is the European Enforcement Order, stating that the writ of execution is suitable for execution in another country of the European Union, but this is due to the fact that some people moved their centre of life and property there. If there are any court decisions against them that cannot be enforced for these reasons, then courts issue European Enforcement Order certificates and have no problem with that. But it is difficult to have a problem with this, because it is a non-contentious procedure on the official form, so everyone is able to master it.

From the perspective of advocates and legal advisers, international issues most often appear in courts in criminal cases, and less often in civil cases, including family cases. In fact, it is not mentioned that international elements were encountered in various types of court proceedings in economic matters, including commercial ones. The courts' and lawyers' lack of recognition of international elements in commercial law cases results from the prevalence of non-national elements. Often in economic matters, there are foreign parties, documents from abroad, or foreign receivables. Also in non-litigious proceedings, it is a typical situation that partners or shareholders are foreign persons. Due to the commonness of foreign elements, they do not arouse interest or surprise; they are treated as routine elements on a par with Polish ones. Administrative law matters are generally outside the jurisdiction of common courts; hence, it is impossible to find foreign elements among them.

The subjective feelings of Polish lawyers and legal advisers are reflected in the statistical reality. The provided public data confirm the limited interest of courts in cases of international scope. The respondents do not testify to the quality of handling such cases, but indicate that there are few of them; and the relevant statistics are highly inaccurate.

Data provided by Polish courts to the Ministry of Justice (*Ministerstwo Sprawiedliwości*) are based solely on court registers³³, and do not take into account empirical reality, but only statistical (quantitative) reality. Theoretically, they should be based on special registers of international cases called Oz and Kop lists, which should be kept in all courts, as well as in prosecutors' offices. Thus, the data should include every element in the field of foreign affairs, from entire cases to court auxiliary activities, e.g., delivery of

³³ *Informator Statystyczny Wymiaru Sprawiedliwości.*

correspondence³⁴. However, there is no standardized method of supplementing the register with further cases and other activities. Hence, court staff complete it at their discretion. Consequently, the register may exclude whole cases carried out abroad, as well as individual technical elements (such as service or requests for legal aid abroad) and elements of the procedure (e.g., hearing a witness or the presence of a foreign party). Due to the lack of guidelines and the multitude of court registers, employees often do not enter anything into the register, or fail to complete it; or they complete it accidentally. In fact, currently all Polish courts keep registers in electronic form, while the Oz and Kop registers usually remain in the traditional form. Due to the courts' use of Currenda information systems, there is a limited possibility of marking international elements in the system. This is because this system only recognizes a few international affairs activities (small claims, the European Enforcement Order, European Payment Order, European Account Preservation Order, and maintenance obligations)³⁵. In other (numerous) cases, the system does not recognize the cases' international aspect³⁶. As a consequence, the statistics produced by the courts and transmitted to the ministry show foreign affairs to a very limited extent; or alternatively, the statistics are only applicable to certain institutions and situations. However, such data are very inaccurate and random.

National ministerial information on Oz matters is prepared annually only in relation to the European Arrest Warrant. This level does not collect data on other international legal procedures and instruments. Therefore, it should be summarized that only this institution of EU law has become established in Poland permanently; and this is directly perceived and understood by all lawyers and citizens as related to international legal proceedings. Over the last few years, the number of cases of applying the EAW has been stable in terms of its execution by Polish courts, and its implementation. It seems that this is the best example of the integration of the Polish judiciary with the courts of other Community countries, EU law, and the institutions of the European Union. It is the EAW that symbolizes the globalization of the procedures for applying and enforcing the law in Poland, and demonstrates that the most important concerns in the globalization processes of the judiciary are the passage of time, and constant implementation and participation in wider integration processes. Unfortunately, this is the only procedure that has become truly established in the Polish judiciary. The statistics of

³⁴ Zarządzenie Ministra Sprawiedliwości z dnia 19 czerwca 2019 r. w sprawie organizacji i zakresu działania sekretariatów sądowych oraz innych działów administracji sądowej.

³⁵ M. Ślęzak, *Regulacje ułatwiające dochodzenie roszczeń cywilnych na obszarze rynku wewnętrznego Unii Europejskiej*, „Gdańskie Studia Międzynarodowe” 2017, t. 15, nr 1–2, s. 196–202.

³⁶ *Sprawozdanie MS-KOM 23*, Warszawa 2019, s. 9–10.

the Ministry of Justice are silent about other elements of globalization and international procedures, which are also not recognized in the statistics of the Central Statistical Office (*Główny Urząd Statystyczny, GUS*), the Council of Europe, and Eurostat³⁷.

Conclusions

Currently, the Polish judiciary is very resistant to globalization changes, even those taking place through the law and institutions of the European Union. Polish advocates and legal advisers emphasize that foreign affairs are hardly noticeable in Polish courts. As a consequence, the beneficiaries of the justice system, i.e. lawyers and their clients, scarcely notice their functioning. The exception is the European Arrest Warrant (EAW), a symbol of the globalization of the Polish judiciary and integration with the European Union. However, the lack of visibility of elements in the field of international relations inside and outside the courts does not mean that the Polish judiciary is not globalizing. It is obvious that courts follow various procedures introduced by international or national law in relation to external relations. Nevertheless, due to their limited number and importance, they are not very noticeable. As the example of the EAW shows, the situation will change with the progressive integration of the Polish judiciary with the world. External lawyers will be the first to notice the internationalization of the Polish judiciary, as they will have the greatest interest in the proper handling of cases with foreign elements.

Before starting the research, we set up two research hypotheses. The study showed that the hypothesis "Polish courts are subject to very insignificant changes caused by globalization phenomena" is fully confirmed. Despite the implementation of EU and international ideas regarding international court cases into the Polish legal system, these solutions do not change the overall picture of Polish courts. Judges and other court employees do not apply instruments of international law in practice, avoid them or even contradict them. The awareness of their existence and the practice of their implementation are absolutely invisible in the work of judges and entire courts. The only exception is the European Arrest Warrant. All other international solutions of family, civil and criminal law are practically absent from judicial practice. "Slight changes" actually only concern the EAW. In terms of the use of Warrant, the second part of the hypotheses is also timidly confirmed. In other cases, changes are hardly noticed. This applies to almost all courts in Poland, with a slight reservation in favour of the courts of large provincial cities.

³⁷ *Dynamic database of European judicial systems; Eurostat - database; Główny Urząd Statystyczny.*

Unfortunately, the awareness of courts and court staff about the existence and practical use of institutions of international law is also very low and does not increase. Thus, the second posed hypothesis is also fully confirmed. Due to the lack of training, courses, conferences, meetings and proper preparation during court apprenticeship, court employees do not even know what global legal procedures can be implemented in the work of the judiciary. Polish courts have so many obligations and such a great influence that they are unable to taste the formal and informal elements of globalization. Moreover, the complexity of the international matter, the lack of knowledge of foreign languages, the lack of support from public authorities as well as the lack of motivation and need mean that the awareness of judges and other court employees regarding the impact of globalization on the Polish judiciary is negligible.

Unfortunately, in the present years, a certain regression in Poland's integration with European and world structures can be observed. Changes in the Polish constitutional system is also reducing trust and the practice of using international mechanisms; there is also a lack of structural reforms within the judiciary. Lawyers emphasize that the lack of competencies, staff shortages, and the lack of actual communication between Polish judges and other court employees and institutions of the European Union and other countries, contribute to limiting the use of international mechanisms in Polish judicial practice. Without major reforms in the education of lawyers, the structure of the courts, and an increase in court support staff, the problem of not using the potential of globalization will escalate.

In the near future the number of institutions of international law and international practice will increase, but their visibility in Polish courts will still be low. Unfortunately, without knowledge of the globalization mechanisms that are prevalent among court employees, they will not appear in court practice. The widespread reserve, fear and communication difficulties of court employees will deepen the alienation of the Polish judiciary from the Europeanization and globalization processes. Even new EU solutions at various levels will not change Polish practice. Furthermore, migrations of people and capital, for example from Ukraine, will not make Polish judges notice the need to use globalization mechanisms in the everyday practice of judging. The only effective solution is to change the education of lawyers, promote cooperation of courts with European institutions and other countries, and the courts' constant participation in experiencing globalization. This must be a conscious approach, based on experience and competence, rather than passive perception of those elements that spontaneously reach the courts.

However, we must believe that with the increase in migration, there will be a growing need to use international procedures. Over time, they will become so natural in the work of courts that their specific separateness will disappear. Such a phenomenon already occurs in the case of practising commercial law, where international elements are not noticed, although they are extremely numerous. It should be expected that the Europeanization and further globalization of the Polish judiciary will accelerate in the near future, and in only a few years it will be normal for Polish courts to use the entire range of institutions introduced by European Union law.

Literature:

1. Abel R.L., *Lawyers and the power to change*, Oxford 1985.
2. Babbie E.R., *Podstawy badań społecznych*, Warszawa 2008.
3. Berelson B., *Content analysis in communication research*, New York 1971.
4. Błachucki M., *Sądownictwo antymonopolowe w Polsce - historia i ustrój*, Warszawa 2011.
5. Bodio J., *Instytucja asesora sądowego*, „Studia Iuridica Lublinensia” 2010, no. 13.
6. Charmaz K., *Teoria ugruntowana: praktyczny przewodnik po analizie jakościowej*, Warszawa 2013.
7. Chlabicz K., *Postępowanie sporne przed Urzędem Patentowym w przedmiocie unieważnienia praw własności przemysłowej*, „Zeszyty Prawnicze” 2017, t. 17, no. 3.
8. Cholewa J., *Jak język polski i francuski odzwierciedla wzajemne postrzeganie Polaków i Francuzów?* [w:] *Anglosasi, Francuzi i Polacy: wzajemny wizerunek dawniej i dziś*, P. Guzowski, M. Kamecka (red.), Białystok 2005.
9. Domagała P., Semeniuk A., *Prawo międzynarodowe w przepisach wykonawczych do prawa o ustroju sądów powszechnych*, „Kwartalnik Krajowej Szkoły Sądownictwa i Prokuratury” 2020, no. 3 (39).
10. Ereciński T., *Ogólne zagadnienia stosowania prawa obcego przez sądy*, „Problemy Prawne Handlu Zagranicznego / Uniwersytet Śląski” 1995, no. 18.
11. Frankfort-Nachmias C., Nachmias D., *Metody badawcze w naukach społecznych*, Poznań 2001.
12. Frey R., *Europejskie postępowanie w sprawie drobnych roszczeń*, „Prawo i Podatki Unii Europejskiej w Praktyce” 2008, no. 4.
13. Gardocka T., *Europejski Nakaz Aresztowania. Praktyka stosowania europejskiego nakazu aresztowania w Polsce jako państwie wydającym*, Warszawa 2011.

14. *Kolizyjne i procesowe aspekty prawa rodzinnego*, J. Gołaczyński, W. Popiołek (red.), Warszawa 2019.
15. *Europejskie prawo karne*, A. Grzelak (red.), Warszawa 2012.
16. Heydebrand W., *From globalisation of law to law under globalisation [w:] Adapting Legal Cultures*, D. Nelken, J. Feest (red.), Oxford, New York 2001.
17. Hofmański P., *Europejski nakaz aresztowania w teorii i praktyce państw członkowskich Unii Europejskiej*, Warszawa 2008.
18. Horton J., Macve R., Struyven G., *Qualitative Research: Experiences in Using Semi-Structured Interviews [w:] The Real Life Guide to Accounting Research*, C. Humphrey, B. Lee (red.), Oxford 2004.
19. Kathrani P., *Globalisation and law: the effect of globalisation on the domestic interpretation of law.*, „Jurisprudencija” 2009, no. 2 (116).
20. Kędzierski D., *Metodologia i paradygmat polskich szczegółowych nauk prawnych*, „Transformacje Prawa Prywatnego” 2018, no. 3.
21. Klimek L., *European Arrest Warrant*, Cham 2014.
22. Król A., *Europejski nakaz dochodzeniowy jako kompleksowy instrument współpracy w sprawach karnych w Unii Europejskiej*, „Rocznik Administracji Publicznej” 2019, no. 5.
23. Kusak M., *Postępowanie karne w sprawach międzynarodowych: podręcznik praktyczny*, Warszawa 2017.
24. Kvale S., *Prowadzenie wywiadów*, Warszawa 2012.
25. Lipiec S., *Świadczenie międzynarodowych usług prawniczych. Studium socjologiczno-prawne polskich prawników, rozprawa doktorska*, 2020.
26. *Alimenty: komentarz*, W. Maciejko, M. Romańska, M. Karcz, Warszawa 2016.
27. Maziarz J., *O niektórych praktycznych problemach związanych z przywróceniem instytucji asesora sądowego*, „Kwartalnik Krajowej Szkoły Sądownictwa i Prokuratury” 2018, no. 1 (29).
28. McIntosh M.J., Morse J.M., *Situating and Constructing Diversity in Semi-Structured Interviews*, „Global Qualitative Nursing Research” 2015, no. 2.
29. Nicpoń M., Marzęcki R., *Pogłębiony wywiad indywidualny w badaniach politologicznych [w:] Przeszłość, teraźniejszość, przyszłość: problemy badawcze młodych politologów*, Kraków 2010.
30. Nowaczyk P., *Perspektywy rozwoju sądownictwa polubownego w Polsce*, „Kwartalnik ADR” 2009, no. 1 (5).

31. Piasecki K., *Zarys sądowego prawa procesowego Unii Europejskiej*, Warszawa 2009.
32. Pisarek W., *Analiza zawartości prasy*, Kraków 1983.
33. Pisuliński J., *Europejskie prawo cywilne*, Warszawa 2009.
34. Podgórecki A., Kurczewski J., *Zarys socjologii prawa*, Warszawa 1971.
35. *Praktyka stosowania europejskiego nakazu aresztowania w Polsce jako państwie wydającym*, Warszawa 2018.
36. Przybyłowska I., *Wywiad swobodny ze standaryzowaną listą poszukiwanych informacji i możliwości jego zastosowania w badaniach socjologicznych*, „Przegląd Socjologiczny” 1978, no. 30.
37. Puchalska K., *Zróżnicowane polskich regionów w aspekcie bezpośrednich inwestycji zagranicznych*, „Zeszyty Naukowe Wyższej Szkoły Ekonomiczno-Społecznej w Ostrołęce” 2016, no. 21.
38. Qu S.Q., Dumay J., *The qualitative research interview*, „Qualitative Research in Accounting & Management” 2011, t. 8, no. 3.
39. *Sprawozdanie MS-KOM 23*, Warszawa 2019.
40. Steger M.B., *Globalization: A Very Short Introduction*, Oxford 2017.
41. Stępień-Załucka B., *Sprawowanie wymiaru sprawiedliwości przez Sąd Najwyższy w Polsce*, Warszawa 2016.
42. Ślęzak M., *Regulacje ułatwiające dochodzenie roszczeń cywilnych na obszarze rynku wewnętrznego Unii Europejskiej*, „Gdańskie Studia Międzynarodowe” 2017, t. 15, no. 1–2.
43. Tkacz S., *Sędzia jako osoba sprawująca „wymiar sprawiedliwości”*, „Przegląd Prawa i Administracji” 2017, t. 110, no. .
44. Weyembergh A., Armada I., Brière C., *Competition or Cooperation?: State of Play and Future Perspectives on the Relations between Europol, Eurojust and the European Judicial Network*, „New Journal of European Criminal Law” 2015, t. 6, no. 2.
45. *Stosowanie prawa Unii Europejskiej przez sądy*, A. Wróbel (red.), Warszawa 2010, t.1.
46. Wysmułek I., Oleksiyenko O., *Strukturalne zróżnicowanie znajomości języków obcych: wybrane wyniki Polskiego Badania Panelowego POLPAN 1988-2013*, Warszawa 2015.

Webography:

47. *Dynamic database of European judicial systems*, <https://www.coe.int/en/web/cepej/dynamic-database-of-european-judicial-systems> [access 18 April 2021 r.].

48. *European Judicial Network (EJN)*, https://www.ejn-crimjust.europa.eu/ejn/EJN_Home.aspx [access 1 April 2021 r.].
49. *Eurostat - database*, <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/data/database> [18 kwietnia 2021 r.].
50. *Główny Urząd Statystyczny*, <https://stat.gov.pl> [access 18 April 2021 r.].
51. *Informator Statystyczny Wymiaru Sprawiedliwości*, <https://isws.ms.gov.pl/pl/baza-statystyczna/> [access 18 April 2021 r.].
52. Kloc K., *Język obcy a praca w zawodzie prawnika*, https://www.goldenline.pl/grupy/Przedsiębiorcy_biznesmeni/prawo/jezyk-obcy-a-praca-w-zawodzie-prawnika,1770622/ [access 16 April 2021 r.].
53. *Krajowy Rejestr Adwokatów i Aplikantów Adwokackich*, <https://rejestradwokatow.pl/adwokat/ewidencja> [access 10 March 2021 r.].
54. *Rejestr radców prawnych*, <https://rejestradcow.pl> [access 10 March 2021 r.].

Legal acts:

55. Rozporządzenie Ministra Sprawiedliwości z dnia 28 stycznia 2002 r. w sprawie szczegółowych czynności sądów w sprawach z zakresu międzynarodowego postępowania cywilnego oraz karnego w stosunkach międzynarodowych (Dz. U. z 2014 r. poz. 1657 z późn. zm.).
56. Ustawa z dnia 6 czerwca 1997 r. Kodeks postępowania karnego (Dz. U. z 2020 r. poz. 30).
57. Ustawa z dnia 27 lipca 2001 r. Prawo o ustroju sądów powszechnych (Dz. U. z 2020 r. poz. 2072).
58. Zarządzenie Ministra Sprawiedliwości z dnia 19 czerwca 2019 r. w sprawie organizacji i zakresu działania sekretariatów sądowych oraz innych działów administracji sądowej (Dz. Urz. MS. 2019. 138 z dnia 2019.06.21).